

Synthesis and antimicrobial activities of some *N*-{4-[5-aryl-1-(isonicotinoyl)pyrazol-3-yl]-phenyl}-benzenesulfonamide and 3-(4-benzenesulfonylaminophenyl)-5-aryl-pyrazole-1-carboxylic acid amide

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Abstract : A series of *N*-{4-[5-aryl-1-(isonicotinoyl)pyrazol-3-yl]-phenyl}-benzenesulfonamide (3a-e) and 3-(4-benzenesulfonylaminophenyl)-5-aryl-pyrazole-1-carboxylic acid amide (4a-e) have been synthesized by refluxing *N*-[4-(2,3-dibromo-3-aryl-propanoyl)-phenyl]-benzenesulfonamide (2a-e) with isonicotinoic acid hydrazide and semicarbazide hydrochloride respectively in pyridine medium. The synthesized compounds were assayed for antibacterial activities against *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram +ve), *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus mirabilis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (gram -ve) and antifungal activities against *Aspergillus niger*.

Keywords : Pyrazole, benzenesulfonamide, antimicrobial activities.

Introduction

Amongst the many five membered heterocycles, considerable interest has been focused on the pyrazole nucleus, which is known to possess a broad spectrum of biological properties such as hypoglycemic¹, cytotoxic², anti-malarial³ and antidepressant⁴ activities. Furthermore 3,5-diarylpyrazole has been identified as active core structure in antibacterial, analgesic, anti-inflammatory and antifungal agents⁵⁻¹⁰. The discovery of this class of drugs provides an outstanding case history of modern drug development and points out unpredictability in biological activities. Benzenesulfonamides substituted on N of sulphonamido group such as, sulphathiazole, sulphapyridine, sulphadiazine etc. are known to possess broad spectrum of biological properties¹¹. Sulfonamides linked to pyrazole, isoxazole, furanone ring possess cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) inhibitor activities and constitute present day Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAID) such as Celecoxib¹², Rofecoxib¹³ and Valdecoxib¹⁴.

Synthetically 3,5-diarylpyrazole derivatives can be obtained by the action of hydrazine/hydrazine derivatives

on 1,3-diketones¹⁵ or flavones¹⁶ or chalcone dibromides¹⁷ or chalcone epoxides¹⁸ in various solvents like ethanol, acetic acid and triethanolamine¹⁹. Prompted by these observations it was contemplated to synthesize a series of benzenesulfonamide derivatives which is some how linked to pyrazole nucleus. We herein reports the synthesis and antimicrobial activities of the titled compounds.

Results and discussion

The starting material *N*-[4-(3-aryl-acryloyl)-phenyl]-benzenesulfonamide (1a-e) were prepared by Claisen-Schmidt condensation of *N*-(4-acetyl-phenyl)-benzenesulfonamide with aromatic aldehydes as per the reported procedure²⁰. Compounds (1a-e) were treated with Br₂/AcOH at room temperature to give *N*-[4-(2,3-dibromo-3-aryl-propanoyl)-phenyl]-benzenesulfonamide (2a-e). Compounds (2a-e) were heated under reflux with isonicotinoic acid hydrazide and semicarbazide hydrochloride in pyridine medium to get (3a-e) and (4a-e) respectively. Physical data of the synthesized compounds are reported in Table 1.

Scheme

Table 1. Physical data of the synthesized compounds

Compd.	R ¹	R ²	Mol. formula	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)
1a	H	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ NO ₃ S	68	180
1b	OCH ₃	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NO ₄ S	78	187
1c	N(CH ₃) ₂	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	72	196
1d	OH	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ NO ₄ S	70	154
1e	OH	OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NO ₅ S	75	135
2a	H	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ NO ₃ SBr ₂	70	170
2b	OCH ₃	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NO ₄ SBr ₂	80	150
2c	N(CH ₃) ₂	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃ SBr ₂	60	165
2d	OH	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ NO ₄ SBr ₂	63	160
2e	OH	OCH ₃	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NO ₄ SBr ₂	61	155
3a	H	H	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ S	60	260
3b	OCH ₃	H	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	70	240
3c	N(CH ₃) ₂	H	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ N ₅ O ₃ S	52	175
3d	OH	H	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	59	> 275
3e	OH	OCH ₃	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₅ S	50	145
4a	H	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S	62	225
4b	OCH ₃	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	63	230
4c	N(CH ₃) ₂	H	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₃ S	58	180
4d	OH	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	61	> 275
4e	OH	OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅ S	62	150

Note

Synthesized compounds were characterized by combined application of IR, ^1H NMR and Mass spectroscopy. The IR spectra of the compounds **2a** and **2b** showed sharp band at 1685 and 1659 cm^{-1} respectively due to C=O stretch where as those of **1a** and **1b** were observed at 1647 and 1649 cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR spectra of the compounds **2a** and **2b** revealed the presence of two doublets (2H) in the range of δ 4.80–5.70. This can be attributed to the presence of -CHBr-CHBr- as the signal due to these protons shifts upfield (as compared to -CH=CH- in **1a** and **1b**) from aromatic range. The signals for NH protons are not observed in case of **2a** and **2b**. Probably it may appear much downfield (above δ 10). IR spectra of compound **3a** and **3b** showed characteristic band at \sim 1615 cm^{-1} , attributed to isonicotinoyl group and \sim 1585 cm^{-1} attributed to C=N stretch in pyrazole ring. ^1H NMR spectra of **3a** and **3b** showed a characteristic singlet at \sim δ 6.87 (1H) for =CH of pyrazole. IR spectra of compound **4a** and **4b** showed characteristic band at \sim 1615 cm^{-1} (C=O stretch, amide I) and \sim 1595 cm^{-1} (N-H bend, amide II) attributed to -CONH₂ group. ^1H NMR spectra of **4a** and **4b** showed a characteristic singlet at \sim δ 6.70 (1H) for =C-H of pyrazole and a singlet at \sim δ 9.6 (2H) attributed to the presence of -CONH₂ group. Mass spectra of the compounds showed molecular ion peak at their respective values.

Experimental

All common reagents and solvents were used as obtained from commercial suppliers without further purification. All melting points were taken in open capillary in silicon oil bath and are uncorrected. Homogeneity of the synthesized compounds was checked on pre-coated TLC plates and spots were visualized using UV chamber. IR spectra were recorded on Nicolet-Impact 400 FTIR spectrometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker AC-300 FNMR (300 MHz) using TMS as internal standard. ESI Mass spectra were recorded on Bruker micro TOF-Q spectrometer.

N-[4-(2,3-Dibromo-3-phenyl-propanoyl)-phenyl]-benzenesulfonamide (**2a**) :

To a suspension of *N*-[4-(3-phenyl-acryloyl)-phenyl]-benzenesulfonamide (**1a**) (3.63 g, 0.01 mol) in acetic acid (10 mL), solution of bromine in acetic acid (30% v/v) was added dropwise with constant stirring until the reac-

tion mixture appears dark brown. It was stirred for half an hour at room temperature. The solid obtained was filtered and washed with petroleum ether to get **2a**. IR : 3236 (NH), 1685 (C=O), 1343 and 1161 (SO₂ asymm. and symm.), 547 cm^{-1} (C-Br); ^1H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 5.62 (1H, d, *J* 12 Hz) and 5.69 (1H, d, *J* 12 Hz), 7.16–7.84 (14H, m, Ar-H); Mass : *m/z* 521.9 (M+H).

N-{4-[2,3-Dibromo-3-(4-methoxy-phenyl)-propionyl]-phenyl}-benzenesulfonamide (**2b**) :

IR : 3243 (NH), 1659 (C=O), 1343 and 1161 (SO₂ asymm. and symm.), 547 cm^{-1} (C-Br); ^1H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 3.83 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 4.84 (1H, d, *J* 12 Hz) and 4.99 (1H, d, *J* 12 Hz), 6.91–7.98 (13H, m, Ar-H); Mass : *m/z* 551.9 (M+H).

N-[4-(5-Phenyl-1-(isonicotinoyl)pyrazol-3-yl)-phenyl]-benzenesulfonamide (**3a**) :

N-[4-(2,3-Dibromo-3-phenyl-propanoyl)-phenyl]-benzenesulfonamide (**2a**) (1.37 g, 0.0025 mol) and isonicotinoic acid hydrazide (0.7 g, 0.005 mol) were refluxed in pyridine (20 ml). After 8 h the TLC showed the complete consumption of **2a**. The reaction mixture was cooled and quenched with acidified water. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with 2% NaHCO₃, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to get **3a**. IR : 3216 (NH), 1618 (C=O), 1337 and 1163 (SO₂ asymm. and symm.); ^1H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 6.77 (1H, s, =CH of pyrazole), 7.15–7.92 (18H, m, Ar-H), 8.61 (1H, s, SO₂NH); Mass : *m/z* 481.1 (M+H).

N-[4-(5-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-1-(isonicotinoyl)pyrazol-3-yl)-phenyl]-benzenesulfonamide (**3b**) :

IR : 3203 (NH), 1614 (C=O), 1580 (C=N), 1339 and 1159 (SO₂ asymm. and symm.); ^1H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 3.85 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 6.90 (1H, s, =CH of pyrazole), 6.91–7.94 (17H, m, Ar-H), 8.2 (1H, s, SO₂NH); Mass : *m/z* 511.1 (M+H).

3-(4-Benzenesulfonylamino-phenyl)-5-phenyl-pyrazole-1-carboxamide (**4a**) :

N-[4-(2,3-Dibromo-3-phenyl-propanoyl)-phenyl]-benzenesulfonamide (**2a**) (1.37 g, 0.0025 mol) and semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.6 g, 0.005 mol) was refluxed in pyridine (20 ml). After 8 h the TLC showed the complete consumption of **2a**. The reaction mixture was cooled and quenched with acidified water. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with 2% NaHCO₃, dried and

Table 2. Antimicrobial data of the synthesized compounds

Microorganism → Compd.	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. mirabilis</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
	(Zone of inhibition in mm)				
2a	6	14	11	–	20
2b	6	13	14	7	17
2c	–	6	–	–	18
2d	6	–	13	7	17
2e	7	–	11	–	19
3a	7	11	6	6	23
3b	7	–	6	–	20
3c	7	–	6	–	24
3d	–	10	–	–	25
3e	–	6	7	–	17
4a	6	11	12	–	21
4b	7	–	–	–	22
4c	–	–	–	–	23
4d	6	7	–	–	22
4e	6	6	–	–	18

–= Inactive.

recrystallized from ethanol to get **4a**. IR : 3295 (NH₂), 3236 (NH), 1616 (C=O stretch, amide I), 1599 (NH bend, amide II), 1337 and 1161 (SO₂ asymm. and symm.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 6.75 (1H, s, =CH of pyrazole), 7.09–7.95 (14H, m, Ar-H), 8.95 (1H, s, SO₂NH), 9.96 (2H, s, NH₂); Mass : *m/z* 441.1 (M+Na).

3-(4-Benzenesulfonylamino)phenyl-5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-pyrazole-1-carboxylic acid amide (4b) :

IR : 3401 (NH₂), 3216 (NH), 1616 (C=O stretch, amide I), 1595 (NH bend, amide II), 1338 and 1160 (SO₂ asymm. and symm.); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 3.80 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 6.70 (1H, s, =CH of pyrazole), 6.84–7.89 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.82 (1H, s, SO₂NH), 9.7 (2H, s, NH₂); Mass : *m/z* 471.1 (M+Na).

Antimicrobial activity :

All the synthesized compounds have been assayed for their antibacterial activities against *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram +ve), *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus mirabilis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (gram –ve) by using paper disc diffusion method²¹ at a concentration of 50 µg/mL. These compounds have been also assayed for their antifungal activities against *Aspergillus niger* at a concentration of 100 µg/mL by cylinder method²². The zone of inhibition was measured in millimeter after 48 h at 30 °C. Most of the compounds are moderately active against *Escherichia*

coli, *Proteus mirabilis* and *Aspergillus niger* and weakly active against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The values are reported in Table 2.

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